

Complex Formation Equilibria of Glycinehydroxamic Acid in Aqueous Organic Solvents

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The complex equilibria of glycinehydroxamic acid (2-amino-*N*-hydroxyacetamide) with proton and some metal ions has been reported in aqueous solution only¹. Glycinehydroxamic acid has been used in the design of metal chelates to supplement trace elements essential in animal nutrition². No information is available in literature regarding complex equilibria study of this ligand with proton and metal ions in mixed solvents. The present study reports the protonation constants of this ligand and stability constants of its metal complexes in aqueous, methanol-water, ethanol-water, isopropanol-water and dioxane-water mixtures at constant mole fraction (0.24) of organic solvent.

Results and Discussion

At constant mole fraction of organic solvent, the protonation constant $\log K_1^H$ (NH_3^+) in various aqueous organic mixtures followed the sequence : dioxane-water > isopropanol water > methanol-water > ethanol-water > water. At mole fraction of 0.24 of organic solvent, structuredness of water³ crosses the maximum value for all the other media and thus has its usual acidity and ionic component of the proton-ligand bond responses to the change in dielectric constant. Glycinehydroxamic acid has two ionisable protons, one from protonated $^+\text{NH}_3$ and other from NHOH group.

The first ionisation of NHOH group leads to formation of species (II) with net charge zero while the

second ionisation of $^+\text{NH}_3$ group gives negatively charged species (III). Born equation⁴ predicts that creation of charge in media of low dielectric constant is an unfavourable process, and thus the equilibria involving (II) \rightleftharpoons (III) should be altered to a greater extent in mixed aqueous organic solvents of varying dielectric constants. The higher $\log K_1^H$ ($^+\text{NH}_3$) values in mixed solvents (Table 1) are explained on the basis of above mentioned considerations. Since the equilibria (I) \rightleftharpoons (II) does not create any charged species, therefore, the value of $\log K_2^H$ (NHOH) are almost similar in mixed solvents. However, the increased $\log K_2^H$ value in dioxane-water mixture may be due to its very low dielectric constant compared to aqueous and aqueous alcoholic mixtures. The value of formation function (\bar{n}) lies between 0 and 2 in aqueous and different aqueous-organic mixture. The metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) data (Table 1) in aqueous medium agree very closely with the previously reported values¹ in aqueous medium. The stability sequence for $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log \beta_2$ values in various mixed solvents was found to be : dioxane-water > isopropanol-water > ethanol-water \approx methanol-water > water, which, in general, is parallel to the order of increase in dielectric constants of the various solvents. It is commonly held that water molecules are preferentially, if not almost exclusively solvated in mixed solvent and the importance of taking into account the elimination of coordinated water molecules or cause contributing to the medium effect has been reported⁵. A reaction of complex formation may be described by the equation,

The increase in stability of ML and ML_2 ($\log K_1$ and 873

$\log K_2$) in an aqueous mixed solvent compared to that in water alone derives in some part from the lower activity of water in the mixed solvent compared to this value in pure water. The greater $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in mixed solvents suggest that ion-ion interaction between the metal ion and the ligand intensifies to a greater extent than ion-dipole interaction between the metal ion and the solvent. Based on $\log \beta_2$ values, the stability order for metal ions in each solvent system was $Zn^{II} > Cd^{II}$, which followed Irving-Williams order of stability of metal complexes⁶.

Experimental

The purity of glycinehydroxamate (2-amino-N-hydroxyacetamide) (Sigma) was checked potentiometrically and its solution was prepared in glass-distilled water. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Metal salts used were of B.D.H. products. Total volume in each case was 20 ml. An EC digital pH meter with combined glass and calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements to an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH units in potentiometric titrations against 0.1 N NaOH. The pH titration technique of Irving and Rossotti⁷ was used to determine protonation constants of the ligand and stability constants of metal-ligand

Fig. 1. Titration curves for glycinehydroxamic acid and metal-glycinehydroxamic acid in methanol-water at 35°C: (o) acid alone, (□) acid + glycinehydroxamic acid, (Δ) acid + glycinehydroxamic acid + Zn^{II} and (●) acid+glycinehydroxamic acid + Cd^{II}.

TABLE 1 – PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF GLYCINEHYDROXAMIC ACID IN AQUEOUS AND AQUEOUS ORGANIC MIXTURES AT CONSTANT MOLE FRACTION OF ORGANIC SOLVENT (0.24)

Ionic strength = 0.15 M (NaCl), Temp. = 35

Cation	Constant	Solvent composition (% v/v)				
		water (100%)	Methanol-water (42.5 : 57.5)	Ethanol-water (51.8 : 48.2)	Isopropanol-water (58.6 : 41.4)	Dioxane-water (61.2 : 38.8)
H ⁺	$\log k_1^H$	9.46	9.91	9.71	9.96	10.74
	$\log k_2^H$	7.39	7.41	7.29	7.42	7.65
	$\log \beta_2^H$	16.85	17.32	17.00	17.38	18.39
Zn ²⁺	$\log k_1$	5.85	6.15	6.16	6.28	6.79
	$\log k_2$	4.56	4.85	4.91	5.08	5.89
	$\log \beta_2$	10.41	11.00	11.07	11.36	12.68
Cd ²⁺	$\log k_1$	4.36	4.65	4.62	5.06	5.54
	$\log k_2$	3.26	3.63	3.68	3.89	4.26
	$\log \beta_2$	7.62	8.28	8.30	8.95	9.80

complexes. The pH values in aquo-organic mixtures were corrected using the method of Van Uitert and Hass⁸. The mixtures (a) concentration of HCl ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$), (b) (a) + concentration of ligand ($2 \times 10^{-3} M$) and (c) (b) + concentration of metal ion ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$) were prepared at constant mole fraction 0.24 of organic solvent in aqueous, methanol-water (42.5 : 57.5%, v/v), ethanol-water (51.8 : 48.2%, v/v), isopropanol-water (58.6 : 41.4%, v/v) and dioxane-water (61.2 : 38.8%, v/v) mixtures at ionic strength of 0.15 M (NaCl) at 35° and titrated against 0.1 N NaOH potentiometry. The titration curves for acid, (acid + ligand) and (acid + ligand + metal) ions were drawn and are shown only for methanol-water mixtures (Fig. 1). The protonation constants and metal-ligand stability constants were calculated by various computational methods⁹ and average values are given in Table 1.

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